

Hyperfine and Exchange Interactions in Tetraethylammoniumbis(maleonitriledithiolato)cuprate(II), [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂][†]

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Single crystal epr study on [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂] diluted into the diamagnetic Ni^{II} analog shows the *g* and *A* tensors to be axially symmetric and to be having coincident principal axes. The pure Cu^{II} salt shows a single exchange narrowed epr line. The anisotropic line widths have been analysed to obtain a value of 1 700 ± 300 G for *J* in this system. The estimate of *J* has been further confirmed by computing and comparing the Fourier components of the spin correlation functions using Blume Hubbard and Anderson-Weiss theoretical models.

THE metal dithiolene complexes of the type [MS₂C₂R₂]ⁿ⁻, where M = Cu and Ni group metals; and R = H, CH₃, CF₃, C₆H₅, CN, etc., have been of considerable interest to chemists as well as physicists for more than two decades. The continued interest stems from the fact that these materials possess unusual structural, magnetic and conducting properties as is evident from the large number of reviews¹⁻⁸ and research publications. Of greater significance is the magnetic properties of maleonitriledithiolato (R = CN, mnt) complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{III} ions⁴⁻⁷. In the past few years, we have been actively involved in the study of such systems using X-ray crystal structure, epr, magnetic susceptibility and optical measurements⁹⁻¹⁰. In this article, we report the exchange and hyperfine interactions in a Cu^{II} complex, namely, tetraethylammoniumbis(maleonitriledithiolato)cuprate(II), [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂].

The compound [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂] is interesting in that it behaves as a semiconductor having a large negative temperature coefficient of resistivity⁶. The resistivity above 300 K is comparable to those of some of the better known wide-band-gap inorganic semiconductors. Magnetic susceptibility measurements show the exchange interaction in this system is too weak to be measured accurately. We have employed epr technique, which is known to be a better tool to study weaker and finer interactions, and demonstrated nicely the effect of exchange modulation on the broadening effects, such as hyperfine and dipolar interactions apart from getting a reasonable estimate for the isotropic exchange coupling constant. The magnetic parameters of the 'isolated' molecule needed for the present work were obtained by diluting the Cu^{II} compound into the isomorphous Ni^{II} analog and these results are also presented in this article, though measurements of this kind have been made by Maki *et al.*¹⁷. However, the present emphasis is to measure these parameters very

accurately. Furthermore, we decided to have a look into the direction cosines of the magnetic parameters since the crystal structures of the host and paramagnetic part have been known subsequent to the earlier work of Maki *et al.*¹⁷.

Experimental

Both the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were synthesised separately according to the published procedure¹⁸. Large red-brown crystals of [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂] were obtained by slow evaporation of a solution of the 'pure' compound in ethanol-water (1 : 1, v/v) mixture. In the case of Ni^{II} compound, large deep-red plates with well developed faces were obtained from acetone-isopropyl alcohol (3 : 1, v/v) solutions of [NEt₄]₂[Ni(mnt)₂] containing 0.5% by weight of the Cu^{II} analog by slow evaporation at 10°.

The isomorphous nature of the lattices was established by measuring the unit cell constants using Enraf-Nonius CAD-4 diffractometer. The morphologies of the crystals were determined by optical goniometer. Though the two systems were isomorphous they were found to grow with different morphologies in the respective solvents.

Single crystal epr measurements were carried out with a Varian E-112 spectrometer operating at X- (~9.5 GHz) and Q-band (~35 GHz) frequencies using 100 kHz field modulation. The crystals were mounted at the end of a quartz rod having an L-shaped wedge using APIEZON-N grease. Rotation of the crystal was done with the use of a goniometer. The spectra were recorded for 10° intervals. DPPH (diphenylpicrylhydrazyl) was used as a *g*-calibrant. The magnetic field was earlier calibrated. All the epr measurements were made at room temperature. The line widths reported in this paper are peak-to-

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peak width of the derivative spectrum, ΔB_{pp} . The error in line width measurement is ± 2 G and that in g -factor is ± 0.002 .

Results and Discussion

Crystal structure: The unit cell parameters of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} compounds are collected in Table 1. It is evident from a comparison of the two sets of values that the two lattices are isomorphous to each other. The crystal structure of the Cu^{II} salt has been reported to be done but it is yet to be published¹⁰. The structure of the Ni^{II} compound has been solved recently in this laboratory²⁰.

TABLE 1—UNIT CELL PARAMETERS OF $[\text{NEt}_4]_2[\text{Cu}(\text{mnt})_2]$ AND $[\text{NEt}_4]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{mnt})_2]$

	$[\text{NEt}_4]_2[\text{Cu}(\text{mnt})_2]$	$[\text{NEt}_4]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{mnt})_2]$
a	7.595 (3) Å	7.5608 (7) Å
b	8.601 (3) Å	8.7017 (9) Å
c	13.111 (5) Å	12.626 (3) Å
α	94.6 (1)°	93.73 (1)°
β	108.1 (1)°	104.27 (1)°
γ	75.6 (1)°	75.257 (9)°
V	789 Å ³	779 Å ³
Z	1	1
space group	$P\bar{1}$	$P\bar{1}$

The structure consists of monomeric anionic units stacked along a -axis of the unit cell. A projection of the packing onto ab plane of the unit cell is shown in Fig. 1. The Ni atom of the anion has an approximate square planar configuration with all the four Ni-S distances equal within experimental error. The whole anion unit is planar to within 0.047 Å. The shortest metal-metal contact is along the stack axis, a (~ 7.6 Å).

Fig. 1. Projection of the structure of $[\text{NEt}_4]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{mnt})_2]$ onto ab plane. The circles refer to $[\text{NEt}_4]^+$ ions.

By virtue of the triclinic space group $P\bar{1}$ with $Z=1$, we have only one set of magnetically equivalent site in this lattice.

Epr of Cu^{II} diluted in $[\text{NEt}_4]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{mnt})_2]$: The single crystal X-band epr measurements were made by rotating the crystal, in a fixed magnetic field vector, with respect to three orthogonal axes X, Y and Z. At all orientations one could observe two sets of four sharp lines; the two sets due to the presence of the two isotopes of copper, namely, ^{63}Cu (69.09%) and ^{65}Cu (30.91%) and four lines in each set due to $I=3/2$ of both the isotopes. A typical single crystal spectrum is shown in Fig. 2. It must be noted that since the magnetic moments of the two isotopes of copper are nearly equal (+2.226 and +2.385 B.M. for ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu , respectively) usually either the lines will be overlapping with each other making the analysis difficult or

Fig. 2. X-band epr spectrum with $B \parallel g_z$. The lines marked with * are those of ^{65}Cu isotope (30.91%).

the lines due to the less abundant ^{65}Cu will be ignored in the interpretation of the spectra. However, in the present case, the resonances were very sharp such that the two sets of lines could be very clearly resolved without any overlap between them, particularly the outer most ones.

The angular variations of the g -factor in XY, YZ and ZX planes are shown in Fig. 3. The measured g -values were used to construct the

Fig. 3. Angular variation of g in (x) XY-, (O) YZ- and (●) ZX- planes. The solid curves are the least-squares fit to the experimental points in the respective planes.

g^2 -matrix using a least squares minimisation procedure and this matrix was then diagonalised by Jacobi's method to get the principal values of g -tensor and their direction cosines with respect to the laboratory frame work X, Y and Z. The principal values and their direction cosines are listed in Table 2. The g -tensor can be considered

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL g AND A VALUES* AND THEIR DIRECTION COSINES

Parameter	Direction cosines		
	X	Y	Z
$g_x = 2.029$	0.581	-0.410	0.742
$g_y = 2.026$	0.257	0.912	0.890
$g_z = 2.085$	0.808	-0.021	-0.589
$A_1(^{63}\text{Cu}) = 162$	0.795	-0.013	-0.607
$A_1(^{65}\text{Cu}) = 89$	—	—	—
$A_1(^{63}\text{Cu}) = 174$	0.799	-0.013	-0.601
$A_1(^{65}\text{Cu}) = 42$	—	—	—

* A values in 10^{-4} cm^{-1} ; error in g -factor measurements = ± 0.002 ; error in A values = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

as almost axially symmetric, though there is a slight rhombicity. These values agree well with those reported for Cu^{II} diluted in $[\text{NBu}_4]_2\text{Ni}(\text{mnt})_2$ by Maki *et al.*¹⁷.

The angular variations of $A(^{63}\text{Cu})$ and $A(^{65}\text{Cu})$ in YZ, ZX and XY planes are given in Figs. 4, 5 and 6, respectively. Comparison of the g - and A -variations in the respective planes shows that the two tensors have coinciding principal axes directions, within experimental error ($\pm 3^\circ$). To the

Fig. 4. Angular variation of A for $(\bullet)$ ^{63}Cu and $(\circ)$ ^{65}Cu isotopes in YZ-plane.

first order, the transition energies for a system with axial g - and hyperfine splitting tensors would be

$$h\nu(\theta) = \beta g(\theta) [B_0 + K(\theta)m] \quad (1)$$

where, $h\nu$ is the transition energy in ergs, B_0 is the strength of the applied magnetic field, θ is the angle that B_0 makes with g_z , and m is the allowed values of I . $K(\theta)$ is the angle dependent hyperfine splitting parameter in Gauss given by

$$g(\theta)^4 g(\theta)^2 = A_1^2 g_1^2 \cos^2 \theta + A_1^2 g_1^2 \sin^2 \theta \quad (2)$$

The values of $g(\theta)^4$ $K(\theta)^2$ were used in the same manner as with $g^2(\theta)$ to get the principal values of

Fig. 5. Angular variation of A for $(\bullet)$ ^{63}Cu and $(\circ)$ ^{65}Cu isotopes in ZX-plane.

Fig. 6. Angular variation of A for $(\bullet)$ ^{63}Cu and $(\circ)$ ^{65}Cu isotopes in XY-plane.

($g^4 K^2$) tensor and hence the A -tensor. The results are given in Table 2. It must be mentioned that we could get identical direction cosines for the z -components of g and A . In the case of X-Y ($\perp$) components due to the axially symmetric nature of A we could not get any meaningful direction cosines.

The relative values of A for the two isotopes $A_1(^{65}\text{Cu})/A_1(^{63}\text{Cu})$ (1.072) and $A_1(^{65}\text{Cu})/A_1(^{63}\text{Cu})$ (1.070) are in excellent agreement with the ratio of their magnetic moments, $\mu(^{65}\text{Cu})/\mu(^{63}\text{Cu})$ (1.071). To our knowledge, this is the first case of this type of systems where the hyperfine tensor for the less abundant ^{65}Cu nucleus is reported. In earlier studies, either ^{65}Cu splitting has been ignored due to poor resolution¹⁷ or studies have been done with ^{63}Cu enriched sample⁵.

Another interesting aspect of the present study is the observation of 'spin-flip' and 'forbidden' transitions, the latter being due to the quadrupolar nature of the Cu nuclei. However, analysis of these features are not discussed herein.

Epr of pure [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂]:

g-tensor: A single exchange narrowed epr line with nearly Lorentzian shape was observed at all orientations and at both X- and Q-band frequencies. The observed *g* values in the three orthogonal planes were used to set up the *g*²-matrix by a least-squares procedure. This matrix on diagonalisation yielded the principal *g* values and their direction cosines with respect to the rotation axes *b*, *a*^{*} and *c*^{*} defined as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} b &= b \\ c^* &= b \times a \\ a^* &= b \times c^* \end{aligned}$$

The results along with direction cosines calculated from the crystal structure are given in Table 3 for comparison. The agreement between the experimental and calculated direction cosines is very good.

TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL *g* VALUES AND THEIR DIRECTION COSINES FOR [NEt₄]₂[Cu(mnt)₂]

Principal <i>g</i> values	Direction cosines					
	Observed			Calculated		
	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i> [*]	<i>c</i> [*]	<i>b</i>	<i>a</i> [*]	<i>c</i> [*]
<i>g</i> _x = 2.019	0.591	0.804	-0.058	0.619	0.785	-0.025
<i>g</i> _y = 2.021	0.410	-0.858	-0.899	0.424	-0.961	-0.891
<i>g</i> _z = 2.086	-0.695	0.475	-0.540	-0.661	0.508	-0.556

Line width: The angular variations of the peak-to-peak derivative line width (ΔB_{pp}) in the three planes at X-band are shown in Fig. 7. No significant difference in line width was observed at Q-band frequency. This along with the fact that magnetic susceptibility measurements⁶ show weakly

Fig. 7. Angular variation of the experimental line width in (○) *a*^{*}*c*^{*}, (×) *c*^{*}*b* and (●) *ba*^{*} planes. The solid lines are the simulated variations in the respective planes using equation (8) with *J* = 1700 G.

coupled spins suggests that the exchange interaction is weak and smaller than the two Zeeman frequencies. Hence, the relative magnitude of the various interactions are given as

$$\mathcal{H}_z^0 > \mathcal{H}_z^x > \mathcal{H}_{ex} > \mathcal{H}_{hy} > \mathcal{H}_{dip}$$

Though $\mathcal{H}_{ex}$ is smaller, it is still sufficiently larger to modulate the broadening effects of hyperfine and dipolar interactions, resulting in a single and sharp resonance.

The line widths are, however, temperature dependent and decrease smoothly as the crystal is cooled⁶.

Line width analysis: For strong exchange narrowing cases, the observed line width is related to the isotropic exchange coupling constant *J* by Van Vleck's²² expression as

$$\sqrt{3}/2 \Delta B_{pp} = M_2^t / J \tag{3}$$

where M_2^t is, in general, the sum of the secular and non-secular second moments of hyperfine and dipolar interactions. The full second moment is used when $\mathcal{H}_{ex} > \mathcal{H}_z$ while only the secular moments will be effective in contributing to the observed line width when $\mathcal{H}_{ex} < \mathcal{H}_z$. In the intermediate case $\mathcal{H}_z < \mathcal{H}_{ex} < \mathcal{H}_z^0$, one would observe frequency dependent non-secular contribution and hence width.

In the present case we have to consider only the secular part of the second moments and hence we write

$$M_2^t = M_2^{hy}(\text{sec.}) + M_2^{dip}(\text{sec.}) \tag{4}$$

The secular part of the dipolar second moment for *S* = 1/2 is given by

$$M_2^{dip}(\text{sec.}) = \frac{9\bar{g}^4 \beta^4}{16h^2} \sum_{i \neq j} (3 \cos^2 \psi_{ij} - 1)^2 r_{ij}^{-6} \tag{5}$$

where, $\bar{g}^2 = (g_1^2 + 2g_2^2)/3$, and ψ_{ij} is the angle between r_{ij} (the vector connecting the dipolar coupled spins) and the effective field *gB*₀. For an orientation (θ, ϕ) of *B*₀, the effective field angles (ψ, ϕ) are

$$\cos \psi = [g_1/g(\theta)] \cos \theta \tag{6}$$

The hyperfine second moment for *I* = 3/2 is given by

$$M_2^{hy}(\text{sec.}) = \frac{5}{4} K^2(\theta) / g^2(\theta) \tag{7}$$

where, $g^2(\theta) = g_2^2 \cos^2 \theta + g_1^2 \sin^2 \theta$ (8)

$$K^2(\theta) = A_{||}^2 g_2^2 \cos^2 \theta + A_{\perp}^2 g_1^2 \sin^2 \theta \tag{9}$$

The dipolar and hyperfine second moments were computed for each orientation from a knowledge of the atomic coordinates given by the crystal structure²⁰ and by using the molecular principal values of *g*- and *A*-tensors obtained from doped single crystal studies (*vide infra*). For computational simplicity axial symmetry was assumed in the case of *g*-tensor and only the ⁶³Cu hyperfine tensor was used. The computed second moments were then fitted with the experimental line widths by using equation (3) to obtain a value of 1700 ± 300 G for *J*. The agreement between the simulated line widths for *J* = 1700 G and the experimental values is remarkably good as is seen in Fig. 7. Though in principle *J* can be obtained from a single measurement, it is gratifying to note that the estimate holds good for all orientations and in all the three planes with a fair degree of precision.

Fourier components :

The hyperfine coupling involves two-spin correlation functions of the form,

$$C_{ij}(t) = [3/S(S+1)] \langle S_i^z S_j^z(0) \rangle \quad (10)$$

where, i and j refer to various sites in the lattice and its contribution to line width, Γ_h (half width at half height) is given by

$$\Gamma_h = \int_0^\infty (a^{(0)} + a^{(1)} \cos \omega_0 t) C(t) dt \quad (11)$$

In the above expression, $a^{(0)}$ and $a^{(1)}$ are the secular ($\Delta m=0$) and non-secular ($\Delta m = \pm 1$) hyperfine second moments, respectively while ω_0 is the Zeeman frequency. $C(t)$ is the autocorrelation function for $i=j$. In the high temperature limit, Γ_h is given by

$$\Gamma_h = a^{(0)} g(0) + a^{(1)} g(\omega_0) \quad (12)$$

where, $g(\omega)$ are the Fourier components of the autocorrelation function $C(t)$ given by

$$2g(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} C(t) \exp(i\omega t) dt \quad (13)$$

The dipolar interactions, on the other hand, leads to four-spin correlation functions given by

$$C_{ijkl}(t) = [3/2 S(S+1)]^2 \langle S_i^+(t) S_j^+(t) S_k^-(0) S_l^-(0) \rangle \quad (14)$$

where, i, j, k and l refer to the sites in the lattice with $i \neq j$ and $k \neq l$. Taking only the diagonal correlation and further using strong decoupling approximation we get

$$C_{ijkl}(t) \propto \langle S_i^+(t) S_i^-(0) \rangle^2 \propto C^2(t) \quad (15)$$

The dipolar contribution to the observed line width, Γ_d is given as

$$\Gamma_d = M_2^{(0)} f(0) + M_2^{(1)} f(\omega_0) + M_2^{(2)} f(2\omega_0) \quad (16)$$

where, $M_2^{(0)}$, $M_2^{(1)}$ and $M_2^{(2)}$ are respectively the secular ($\Delta m=0$) and non-secular ($\Delta m = \pm 1, \pm 2$) dipolar second moments while $f(\omega)$ are the Fourier components of $C^2(t)$ given by

$$2f(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} C^2(t) \exp(i\omega t) dt \quad (17)$$

Now the total contribution to the observed peak-to-peak derivative width, ΔB_{pp} is given as

$$\Gamma_{\text{total}} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \Delta B_{pp} = \Gamma_h + \Gamma_d \quad (18)$$

In the present case, since $\mathcal{H}_{\text{ex}} \ll \mathcal{H}_z$, one can ignore the non-secular broadenings and hence, equation (18) becomes

$$\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \Delta B_{pp} = a^{(0)} g(0) + M_2^{(0)} f(0) \quad (19)$$

Since the spin correlations arising from $\mathcal{H}_{\text{ex}}$ are isotropic the angular dependent line widths provide enough equations to obtain the individual Fourier components.

The ΔB_{pp} values in the a^*c^* plane were fitted into the expression by a least-squares procedure to

get

$$g(0) = 0.60 \pm 0.05 \times 10^{-8} \text{ G}^{-1} \text{ and}$$

$$f(0) = 0.70 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-8} \text{ G}^{-1}.$$

The agreement between the least-squares curve and the experimental values is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Experimental and theoretical line width variation in the a^*c^* -plane: (●) experimental points; (—) least squares fit to the experimental points in the evaluation of $g(0)$ and $f(0)$ and (---) line width variation based on B-H model with $g(0) = 0.59 \times 10^{-8} \text{ G}^{-1}$ and $f(0) = 0.42 \times 10^{-8} \text{ G}^{-1}$.

The Fourier components of the secular part of the spin correlation functions can be computed from theoretical models like Blume-Hubbard²² and Anderson-Weiss²³. The Blume-Hubbard high temperature approximation of $C(t)$ for $S=1/2$ is

$$C_{\text{BH}}(t) = \cos h^{-2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \hat{J} t \right) \quad (20)$$

where, $\hat{J}$ is the root-mean-square exchange ($\hat{J} = \sqrt{2J}$). The Fourier components of $C(t)$ and $C^2(t)$ are

$$g_{\text{BH}}(0) = 2/\hat{J}$$

$$f_{\text{BH}}(0) = 4/3\hat{J}$$

The Anderson-Weiss proposal of Gaussian $C(t)$ for exchange narrowing is

$$C_G(t) = \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \pi \omega_0^2 t^2 \right] \quad (21)$$

with $\omega_0 = J$. This leads to the following expressions for $g(0)$ and $f(0)$

$$g_G(0) = \frac{1}{\omega_0}$$

$$f_G(0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2} \omega_0}$$

The computed Fourier components for $J=1700 \text{ G}$, obtained from epr line width analysis (*vide infra*), are given in Table 4. These values compare reasonably well with the experimental values. We find

TABLE 4—FOURIER COMPONENTS OF SECULAR SPIN CORRELATION FUNCTIONS

Fourier component	Experimental	B-H model ($\hat{J}=2400 \text{ G}$)	A-W model ($J=1700 \text{ G}$)
$g(0) \times 10^8 \text{ G}^{-1}$	0.60 ± 0.05	0.83	0.59
$f(0) \times 10^8 \text{ G}^{-1}$	0.70 ± 0.10	0.55	0.42

that $g(0)$ is slightly over estimated by B-H model while $f(0)$ is underestimated by both the models.

However, it may be worth noting that we could analyse the results and estimate a reasonable value for the isotropic exchange coupling constant from the single crystal epr data. Also, we have successfully compared and confirmed this value using theoretical models of exchange narrowing phenomena.

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